

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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METHODS

Herbert Simon is considered the founder of the behavioral theory of the firm. (1916–2001) – American economist, Nobel laureate, professor of psychology, computer science and management at Carnegie Mellon University in Pittsburgh, who published the monograph “Administrative Behavior” in 1947. After a series of empirical interdisciplinary studies, G. Simon publishes the results in the work “Models of Man – Social and Rational” (1957), and in 1958, together with J. March, a fundamental study “Organizations”. Based on theoretical and practical research, G. Simon developed the theory of normative algorithms for “correct” decisions in such works such as *The Science of the Artificial* (1969), *How People Solve Problems* (with A. Newell, 1972), and introduced the concept of “bounded rationality” (bounded rationality) based on the assumption that in conditions of uncertainty environment and limited calculation abilities of economic agents:

- 1) are limited in their ability to accurately define goals and anticipate the consequences of their decisions;
- 2) they try to realize their own goals not all at once, but sequentially;
- 3) choose satisfactory rather than optimal goals that are less than their maximum capabilities.

Bounded rationality is one of the factors in the emergence of opportunism. According to O. Williamson’s definition, this is “the pursuit of personal gain using deceit.”

The methodological basis of the behavioral theory of the company is the model limited (G. Simon) or variable (H. Leibenstein) rationality agent (person). The theory is based on a generalized model of acceptance decisions where the goal is not the realism of the motivation, but the process, i.e. technology, sequence of steps to develop a solution. The focus of behavioral theory research is on the decision-making process of economic agents in conditions of excess information regarding the possibilities of its processing and the impact of these decisions on the development of the company and its behavior in the market.

Behavioral theory tries to study the activities of economic entities in real situations in the absence of a presumption of economic rationality in the market, where it is not the rational, but the conventional that dominates, behavior of agents, subject not only to the target function of maximizing utility or profit, but also to accepted rules and conventions, taking into account traditions, culture, mentality, social norms and developed standards.

The behavioral theory of the firm is based on a huge body of empirical evidence studies conducted by various groups of economists with the goal open the “black box” of a household and a company and show how the real decision-making process is carried out, find out its patterns. To do this, in their research, followers of behavioral theory use methods such as:

- a) mass surveys of managers, employees, owners of companies in search of answers to the question about the reasons for the behavior of a company, an individual entrepreneur or consumer;
- b) laboratory experiments, introductory lectures, trainings, fights, practicing tasks based on real situations;
- c) a description of specific decision-making in departments and divisions of the company;
- d) development of computer models and programs for making real decisions.

The addition of the theory of bounded rationality with the help of experimental research was undertaken by the German economist R. Selten, winner of the Nobel Prize in 1994. In his work “Bounded Rationality” (1990) R. Selten developed a three-level model of decision making: habits – imagination – logical reasoning¹. The solution to the problem may arise from each level – from lowest to highest. Each level of decision-making is accompanied by the problem of choosing the level of aspirations and the zone of proximal development, due to which the agent searches for a solution either out of habit or including imagination, or by logical reasoning. The final choice of agent is determined conditions of the real situation, psychological state and the predominance of those or other purposes.

H. Leibenstein introduced the concept of “X-efficiency”, a principle showing that the company is not able to fully utilize its intellectual potential their employees and achieve maximum efficiency and profit, since intra-company contracts, which are implicit in nature, cannot fully regulate the behavior of an employee striving for his own comfort. The behavioral theory of the firm received logical development in the works of economists J. March and R. Cyert, who defined the firm as a coalition of individuals and divisions. The authors of “The Behavioral Theory of the Firm,” published in 1963, but retaining relevance and great theoretical significance, showed that the behavior of a firm depends on the decisions made by coalition participants and is determined by the

1 Selten R. Bounded Rationality // Journal of Institutional and Theoretical Economics. 1990. Vol. 146. P. 651–653.

goals, expectations and choice of the firm, as well as the degree control over the implementation of the chosen decision². To make decisions in the Cyert-March behavioral model, the firm carries out:

- 1) forecast of demand for your products;
- 2) forecasting the behavior of competitors;
- 3) cost assessment;
- 4) formulation of goals from the above.

The company draws up an action plan and evaluates it for compliance target levels of indicators. If the plan fits, it is accepted; if not approaches, an adjustment is made to clarify the realism of the forecasts and goals.

The subjective arbitrariness of coalition participants is strictly limited by the budget firm, division of responsibilities and competencies of participants within its framework. The coalition agreement changes under the influence of the level of aspirations of the company's participants, thus "the company becomes a set of goals of its divisions." J. March proposed the metaphor of a trash can and presented the decision-making process of a company in the form of flows of problems, conflicts, alternatives, participants, the interaction of which (almost random) determines the future companies. A group of goals of various divisions and participants of the company determines not a maximum, but a certain (satisfactory) level of output and price products, as well as:

- 1) achieving or exceeding a certain level of production volume indicators;
- 2) maintaining the level of stock of components and finished products to avoid shortages and stoppages of technological processes;
- 3) the desired level of sales and markups;
- 4) market share, stability and prestige of the company;
- 5) profit, increase in investment.

Note that many leading companies act just the opposite, achieving success through regular monitoring of the environment and constant search and application of technological and institutional innovations.

RESULTS

Summarizing the above, we come to the conclusion that the company as a coalition of participants is forced to find a compromise between all interested groups and individual participants and take into account the totality and mutual influence of their goals. Goal alignment is greatly influenced by the presence of intra-company routine, reducing decision-making to accepted and practiced procedures. Sometimes this makes it difficult to achieve a quick and effective result, including taking into account the company's budget limitations, since not the most optimal, but a satisfactory result is accepted, compared not with new alternative solutions, but with the previous one that did not work a procedure or technology that may benefit individual participants exhibiting opportunistic behavior. The company's routine must be consistent with the interests of development and survival. Inheritance and transmission of routines constitute an essential part of knowledge assets firm and its market value. Conflicts that arise within a company are due to different interests and the goals of the main influence groups, which determines the trajectory of the company's development and the direction of its activities. Professor of Management from a Canadian University McGill G. Mintzberg considers the interaction of groups through a hierarchical functional system of the company in the following form:

- 1) senior management, strategists;
- 2) operators who produce the product and services;
- 3) line managers who coordinate production and activities;
- 4) analysts who are developing a planning and control system;
- 5) support personnel who provide indirect support to production;
- 6) ideologists.

Each of the influence groups performs its functions to achieve its own goals. Mintzberg's group conducted one of the most rigorous studies of how successful executives manage their time³. Personal interests do not

² Cyert R., March J. A Behavioral Theory of the Firm. Englewood Cliffs. 1963. P. 27–28.

³ Mintzberg H. The Nature of Managerial Work. N.Y.: Harper & Row, 1973. P. 31–35.

allow top managers to spend much time on planning, organizing, motivating and controlling the company. For one problem. According to Mintzberg, a manager spends an average of 9 minutes a day. Economists Luffman and Newbould highlight the interests of the main participants in the coalition agreements, stakeholders, depending on their influence and direction of activity:

participants, shareholders, institutional investors	Rate of return on capital. Market value of the investment. Dividend stability
managers	Increase in turnover. Increase in assets. Profit stability. Amount of workers
employees	Labor intensity. Salary growth rate. Dependence of salary growth from profit growth
economic partners, buyers, suppliers	Relationship stability. Execution of obligations. Variety of choice. Product safety

Influence on the company's decisions by external stakeholders and internal participants of the company – is characterized (according to D. Mendelow's model) as economic power of an agent, coupled with the opportunity and desire, interest to use it. In the studies of I. Adizes, one can find a description of intra-company conflicts of interest between four groups of company participants, whose functions are as follows:

- a) produce results;
- b) administer;
- c) be an entrepreneur;
- d) integrate⁴.

The mutually agreed upon and consistent implementation of these roles helps ensure that the firm remains effective and successful over the long term, time, and the predominance of one of the above functions at one time or another period of the company's life, for example, strict administration at an early stage development of the company, or the absence of any functions, for example, entrepreneurial, lead to premature aging and fading of the life cycle companies.

DISCUSSION

American psychologist K. Graves (Union College), taking as a basis the development of a person's value system, together with his followers D. Beck and K. Cowan developed a socio-evolutionary theory – spiral dynamics. Levels of development in the theory of spiral dynamics are described through paradigms of consciousness, value complexes, spiritual beliefs, culture, moral principles, models of behavior and learning that arise as the need for them arises in the process of sociocultural evolution. The model is hierarchical, color coding from beige to yellow is introduced, values it proceeds in order of increasing complexity, where the highest stage of development is unknown, and the turns of the spiral alternate with an orientation towards individual or collective values⁵.

Turquoise	The big picture, holistic	World-organism	
Yellow	Economical, flexibility	Kaleidoscope world	
Green	Relationship, agreement, community, ecology	Harmony	Relationship management
Orange	Success, strategy, growth, image	World-mechanism	Project management
Blue	The forces of truth authoritarianism, discipline, laws	Order	Structure management
Red	Strength, conquest, leadership	Jungle	People management
Violet	Genus, related souls, family	Magic	
Beige	Survival	Instincts	

4 Адизес И. Как преодолеть кризисы менеджмента. Стокгольмская школа экономики. СПб., 2006. С. 99–101.

5 URL: www.management.com.ua.

Changes in the organizational structure and culture of a company as it is born, grows, matures and ages can be compared to the turns of a multi-colored spirals. Each level of development of a company has its own values, its own the specificity of the color of the revolution from the model of K. Graves, but at the same time the levels of development of various divisions of the company and individual agents may be different, i.e. have various colors, characteristics and decision-making technologies including because of the functions they perform. President of the Euroindex company V. Pekar in his article “Colorful Organizations”⁶, speaking about the “color” of the company, charges for the basis of the characteristics of companies, the corresponding methods of organization, leadership and management (such as purple family, red plan, blue hierarchy, yellow network), while it is clear that companies of “pure colors” do not exist, so How do the characteristics of different types of both coalitions and individuals manifest themselves? participants, i.e. in one company, participants can be of different sociocultural backgrounds levels, different “colors”. Thus, the firm as a coalition of participants with different goals, different experience, diverse knowledge assets and unequal sociocultural level of development can be represented as a set of many spirals (in a simplified model there are three groups of spirals – shareholders, managers, performers), where each agent is at its own turn of development of the socio-evolutionary spiral and acquires its own color. The contact between the spirals ensures contacts, interaction between participants at different levels, and due to hierarchy and specifics of the company’s work, the spirals of shareholders in the lower turns of the company’s development more often contact with the spirals of managers and rarely with the spirals of performers; contacts are irregular. When promoting firms to yellow principles and level of interaction of agents and coalitions are changing. Contacts of agents of the same color have the greatest productivity, since the values and interests of the agents in this case are close. The “color” of a company will largely be determined by the predominance of the colors of its divisions and participants. Note that the transaction costs of concluding contracts between firms of different colors increase, including due to the need to spend on finding common ground and explaining the positions of the parties. The presence of agents and participants of the company of different “colors”, on the one hand, gives rise to a conflict of interests and values, on the other hand, can play a positive role in solving problems, where the counterparties are participants of a similar color, i.e. the principle of “friend or foe” begins to be applied, where mentality, values, principles of decision-making, previous experience and behavior of agents provide the conclusion necessary agreements and finding compromises. For example, employees – former military personnel find a “common language” with former military personnel from another firm faster than non-serving members of the firm. Shareholders, managers who have hobbies, hobbies, and sports are more successful in establishing contact with a potential investor or counterparty with similar interests, hobbies. We also have to take into account the fact that in many countries decision-making principles of economic agents have a significant impact influence of national culture, mentality. Sometimes, for “national” agents, observing rituals, rules of negotiation, and performing the most difficult “Chinese ceremonies” become more important than the economic essence of the concluded contracts and agreements. When company participants reach a level of well-being at which their basic needs are satisfied (Maslow’s pyramid), they begin to consider new needs and values, including intangible ones, i.e. acquire a new “color”⁷. An agent as a member of a coalition, possessing an indefinite but the expected life time, there is also a choice between utility function and own production function, i.e. he chooses between spending time on work or management (depending on status) and leisure, i.e. the opportunity to use the results of one’s own work in the company.

CONCLUSION

The psychological aspect of an agent’s decision-making is accompanied by the so-called fundamental attribution error, formulated by the Stanford psychologist L. Ross, which manifests itself in the fact that a person, like As a rule, he considers a successful decision to be his merit, and failure as a consequence of external circumstances against which he is powerless. The psychological aspect of an agent’s decision-making is accompanied by the so-called fundamental attribution error, formulated by the Stanford psychologist L. Ross, which manifests itself in the fact that a person, as a rule, he considers a successful decision to be his merit, and failure as a consequence of external circumstances against which he is powerless. The company is heterogeneous in terms of the composition of participants, their roles, interests and goals. Since the resolution of intra-company conflicts occurs through the formation of coalitions according to interests that enter into negotiations, trades and agreements with each other.

Given limited organizational and other resources, in many partnerships decisions by participants are driven by emotions. In large open companies, impersonal bureaucratic procedures are devoted to the fight against emotions. According to I. Mintroff, intra-company agreements are achieved through:

⁶ URL: www.pekar.in.ua

⁷ URL: www.spiraldinamics.org

- persuasion of company participants;
- formation of the participant's requirements;
- participation in discussion and reaching agreement on key issues;
- finding mutual understanding through economic exchange;
- threats of harm to participants;
- forming coalitions with other participants.

In our opinion, in order to conclude intra-company agreements, taking into account the “multiple colors” of participants, constant communications, verbal and non-verbal communication between members of coalitions, rituals and models for making informal decisions (possibly outside of hierarchy and subordination) are needed through the formation experimental units, “neutral sites” with voting rights all participants.

Today, a company can be represented as a union of owners of specific resources, primarily knowledge assets (assuming that it is for this company that they give the greatest return), aiming not only to generate income from their activities, but also self-realization of company participants in the form of achievement intangible, social, subjective goals, priorities and values for knowledge and exploration of the world.

The results of intra-company and inter-coalition conflicts serve as the basis to formulate rules for access to assets and resources controlled by the company. The company develops the rules of the game and goals that can be achieved within an institutionally defined space of possibilities, choices decisions and incentives. The institutional space of the firm retains agents with different economic behavior within the coalition, structures and consolidates socially recognized practices of struggle against various economic interests, thereby ensuring the sustainability of economic activity.

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